

Supporting Information

Ball-Mill Beatdown: Mechanochemical Synthesis of TaON Nanocrystals

Eve K Stegner,¹ Madison R Kuns,¹ Kerly Ochoa-Romero,² Gonzalo Guirado,^{,2} and Javier
Vela^{*,1,3}*

¹Department of Chemistry, Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa 50011, United States;

²Departament de Química, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Cerdanyola del Vallès, 08193
Barcelona, Spain;

³US DOE Ames National Laboratory, Ames, Iowa 50011, United States

vela@iastate.edu

Gonzalo.Guirado@uab.cat

Figure S1. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) size distributions of ball-milled Ta_2O_5 (black), TaON prepared by pre-nitridation ball-milling (green), and TaON prepared by post-nitridation ball-milling (blue).

Figure S2. Size distributions obtained from (a-e) SEM and (f) TEM. TaON nanocrystals prepared from pre-nitridation ball milling are represented in green while TaON nanocrystals prepared from post-nitridation ball milling are represented in blue.

Figure S3. Powder XRD (a) of Ta_2O_5 , TaON, and TaON/ Ta_3N_5 (Ta_3N_5 reflection (023) indicated with black star) nanocrystals along with resulting particle sizes (b–c) from pre-nitridation ball milling (green) and post-nitridation ball milling (blue) (Ta_2O_5 $P2mm$ #9112; TaON $P2_1/c$ #1032; Ta_3N_5 $Cmcm$ #66533).

Figure S4. Sedimentation of Ta_2O_5 and TaON nanocrystals prepared from pre- and post-nitridation ball milling compared to bulk Ta_2O_5 and TaON over the course of 1 h.

Figure S5. Powder XRD (a) and Scherrer size (b) of TaON ball milled from 0 to 4 h.

Figure S6. Color difference between TaON nanocrystals prepared from pre- and post-nitridation ball milling.

Figure S7. SEM-EDS results from post-synthetic ball milling of TaON.

Figure S8. Leftmost graphs display absorbance spectra (a) and Tauc plots (b) of TaON nanocrystals prepared through pre- (green) and post- (in blue) nitridation ball milling. Rightmost graphs display absorption spectra (a) and Tauc plots (b) of TaON ball milled between 0 h and 4 h.

Table S1. Estimation of Bohr radii in tantalum (oxy)nitride semiconductors.^{S1}

Semiconductor	ϵ	m_h^* / kg	m_e^* / kg	m^* / kg	a_B / nm
TaON	25.8	9.66×10^{-31}	2.82×10^{-31}	2.18×10^{-31}	5.7
Ta ₃ N ₅	42.9	1.54×10^{-30}	9.57×10^{-31}	5.90×10^{-31}	3.5

$$m = 9.11 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}; a_0 = 0.0529 \text{ nm}$$

Figure S9. Powder XRD of TaON suspended in water and acid (HCl, pH = 1) for 96 h.

Figure S10. SEM-EDS of TaON nanocrystals (containing 20 weight percent Ta₃N₅) prepared from post-nitridation ball milling.

Material	EDS composition (parameterized to 1 Ta)	N/Ta
TaON	Ta ₁ O _{0.8} N _{0.6}	0.6
TaON/Ta ₃ N ₅	Ta ₁ O _{1.3} N _{1.2}	1.2

Figure S11. Calculated absorption spectra (top) and Tauc plot (bottom) of Ta₂O₅ (black), TaON (green) and TaON containing 14–20 weight percent Ta₃N₅ (orange).

Figure S12. Photoluminescence spectra of TaON and TaON/Ta₃N₅ (slit = 5 nm, λ_{exc} = 500 nm).

Figure S13. (a) Emission profile of 420 nm lamp in respect to TaON absorption spectrum and (b) photocatalytic degradation of bromothymol blue in the presence of TaON/CuO nanocrystals prepared from pre-nitridation ball milling.

Table S3. Bromothymol blue degradation over TiO₂ and TaON-based photocatalysts.

Semiconductor	Cocatalyst	% Degradation	AQY (%) ^c
TiO ₂	CuO	23	0.002
TaON (bulk)	CuO	50	0.004
TaON (nano) ^a	CuO	52	0.005
TaON (nano) ^b	CuO	49	0.004
None	None	15	0.001

^aPrepared from pre-nitridation ball milling. ^bPrepared from post-nitridation ball milling; t = 1 h, λ = 420 nm; 5 mg photocatalyst; 10 mL solution. ^cAQY=100×[Number of reactants consumed/ Number of incident photons (N)].

Figure S14. SEM-EDS images and analysis of TaON coated electrodes.

Figure S15. Cyclic voltammograms (scan rate $0.1 \text{ V} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, RT) recorded on a TaON-modified working Ag (a) and C (b) electrodes showing the baseline and the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 at increasing concentrations in the ionic liquid $[\text{N}_{1114}][\text{TFSI}]$. CO_2 concentration ranges from 0–162 mM and 0–1557 mM for silver and carbon, respectively.

^{S1} Nurlaela, E.; Harb, M.; Gobbo, S.; Vashishta, M.; Takanahe, K. Combined Experimental and Theoretical Assessments of the Lattice Dynamics and Optoelectronics of TaON and Ta_3N_5 . *J. Solid State Chem.* **2015**, *229*, 219–227.